

THE ROLE OF POLITICAL PARTIES "WOMEN'S WING" AND WOMEN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE EDUCATION SECTOR IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN (2017-2025).

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19555441>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 09th April 2026

Accepted: 11th April 2026

Online: 13th April 2026

KEYWORDS

Political activism, education system, political parties, women, local councils, Senate, Oliy Majlis, Higher educational institutions, social state, science, "Women's Wing", gender equality, strategy, Political Council

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the role of political parties "Women's Wing" and women in the development of the education sector in New Uzbekistan, the propaganda activities carried out by active women in parties at various stages of education development, the reforms implemented by the state in the development of education, the privileges granted to women when entering higher educational institutions, and the priority areas of state policy in supporting women in the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy.

In our country, certain reforms have been implemented to further strengthen the system of social protection for women, create the necessary conditions for their education, educate talented and educated girls and increase their scientific potential, improve the legal basis for protecting the rights and legitimate interests of women, increase the socio-economic and political activity of women, and strengthen their role in society, in particular in public administration. Of course, the positive result of these reforms is the roundtable discussions, seminars, trainings, political trainings, and propaganda activities conducted by the Departments for Increasing the Socio-Political Activity of Women and the "Women's Wing" operating within the political parties of our country. As a result of large-scale propaganda activities carried out by the activists of the Women's Political Activity Department of political parties in 2017-2021, the share of women in public administration reached 35 percent, in the field of entrepreneurship - 37 percent, and in the structure of political parties - 49 percent. In addition, the share of women was more than 77 percent in the healthcare system, almost 74 percent in education, 49 percent in trade, almost 46 percent in economic sectors, industry and production, 45 percent in culture and sports, more than 42 percent in agriculture, more than 37 percent in financial and insurance activities, 35 percent in information and communication services, and almost 34 percent in professional, scientific and technical activities. Indeed, in our country, in order for women to find their place in society and to fully enjoy their rights and legitimate interests in all aspects of social life, political trainings and legal consultations are being organized by the Women's Affairs Departments of the parties. In particular, the privileges and preferences provided to women in labor, family, education, social protection,

entrepreneurship development and many other areas have created the basis for not only women but also our country to achieve high indicators in international rankings. As an example, Uzbekistan, having scored 72.8 points in the Gender Equality and Governance Index in 2024, rose from 103rd place in 2022 to 52nd place. Article 50 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates that everyone has the right to education and that the state guarantees free general secondary education and primary vocational education[1].

This, in turn, guarantees the state the right of women to have the same general secondary or secondary specialized education. However, currently, the requirements of the labor market require such education in rare cases. For example, in the case of handicrafts, homemaking, private entrepreneurship, and work as a technical employee in organizations, having the above information and higher education may not be required. However, in the labor market, which is developing day by day and artificial intelligence is replacing natural human intelligence, in order to compete with other personnel, each personnel is required to have at least a higher education. The state has provided a number of privileges for women when enrolling in bachelor's and master's degrees in higher education institutions. In particular, in order to increase the level of coverage of women with higher education, within the framework of the admission indicators to higher educational institutions based on an additional state grant, approved by the Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 402 dated June 23, 2020, women who have a recommendation letter for participation in the competition and have a qualification in accordance with the Regulation on the procedure for organizing their admission to higher educational institutions, as well as laureates of the Zulfiya State Prize from the categories of applicants who have privileges for admission to higher educational institutions, approved by the Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 468 dated June 7, 2019, will have the opportunity to study at the bachelor's level of higher education on a grant basis. For example, in 2024, 4,587 women with five years of work experience and without higher education were given recommendations, and 398 of them were admitted to state higher educational institutions on a paid contract basis. Of course, higher education has a significant impact not only on professional development for women, but also on family well-being. Because, as the Head of our State Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasized, "The education of girls and their higher education serves the prosperity of the entire society." Today, at a new stage of Uzbekistan's development, it is urgent to create broad conditions for women to receive education and actively involve them in science. Of course, higher education has a significant impact not only on professional development for women, but also on family well-being. Because, as the Head of our State Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasized, "The education of girls and their higher education serves the prosperity of the entire society." Today, at a new stage of Uzbekistan's development, it is urgent to create broad conditions for women to receive education and actively involve them in science. In particular, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-87 dated March 7, 2022 "On measures to further accelerate work on systemic support for families and women", a procedure for unconditional reimbursement of contract payments for all women studying at the master's level in state higher educational institutions has been introduced. Thanks to the effective work of the "Women's Wing", organized under the Party's Department for Increasing Women's Political Activity, in order to fully and simply explain this decree to women in the

localities, hundreds of girls were able to study at the master's level during the 2023-2024 academic year. The procedure for using this benefit was regulated by the Regulation on the procedure for reimbursing the fee-contract amount of women admitted to and studying at the master's level of state higher educational institutions on a fee-contract basis from the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by Resolution No. 447 of the Cabinet of Ministers of August 15, 2022.

As a result of the above-mentioned benefits, the share of women among students studying in higher educational institutions of the republic in the 2024/2025 academic year was 52.2 percent. For information, Khorezm region recorded high figures with shares of 62.2%, Navoi region - 58.6%, Syrdarya region - 57.8%. It should be noted that the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-158 dated September 11, 2023, also identifies the support of women as one of the priority areas of state policy. Goal 25 of this strategy pays special attention to ensuring the rights and legitimate interests of women, increasing their social, economic and political activity, and ensuring gender equality. This strategy is aimed at building a New Uzbekistan, creating conditions for every citizen to fully realize their potential, raising an educated and spiritually mature generation, as well as ensuring justice and the rule of law, and further strengthening the position of women in society is put forward as an important task.

In the election program of the SDP of Uzbekistan "Adolat" entitled "Justice is the main criterion of our life, justice is for every person", at the initiative of the "Women's Wing" and the Department for Working with Women in 2017-2019, it was put forward that education is a decisive factor in the development of a modern democratic and tolerant society, that every citizen of Uzbekistan should have the opportunity to receive high-quality and free general education, find a decent job with a good salary, become a good specialist and organize their own business at any time. Therefore, the SDP "Adolat" was a supporter of further strengthening and development of the state higher education system.

In the election program of the "Adolat" Social Democratic Party of Uzbekistan for 2018-2019, the party's main task was to support and develop the best traditions of our country's education system, aimed at the formation of citizens as complete individuals, demonstrating the human factor, and training specialists who meet the demands of the labor market.

Events, seminars, and meetings were organized throughout the republic under the slogan "The teacher is the foundation of the spirituality of society." The fact that 73 percent of employees working in the fields of education, culture, and science and technology, 75 percent in the healthcare system, 42 percent in the manufacturing sector, and 43 percent in agriculture, for the life of our society and the development of the country, are women, shows that they are truly second to none in any field [2].

In the main ideas and practical initiatives put forward in the election programs of UzLiDeP in the field of education for 2015–2019, the activists of the "Women's Wing" party considered it necessary for Uzbekistan to become one of the leading countries in the world in education and intellectual development, and according to them, the main projects are; fully meeting the need for preschool education (in this case, public-private partnerships and non-governmental preschool education organizations will be supported first); providing all kindergartens with computer classes, taking into account the opinions of parents; doubling

the average salary of teaching staff of preschool education organizations and general secondary education institutions; increase the amount of funds paid for more than 153 thousand class leaders in general secondary schools, introduce the state program for the development of schools, create an additional 2.5 million student places by 2030, fundamentally improve the quality of education, double the number of non-state general secondary education organizations, allocate preferential loans in the amount of 1 trillion soums to establish their activities, independent of state organizations introduction of a non-governmental "educational audit" system that is and objectively evaluates; Ideas such as enriching the library fund and full digitization, increasing the effectiveness of scientific research in higher education institutions and increasing the scientific potential to 70%, increasing the share of science-oriented funds in the GDP by 10 times by 2030 [3] have been put forward.

In 2017-2019, the National Revival Democratic Party, deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, activists of the Women's Department, introduced 86 draft laws on the basis of the right of initiative, 64 of which were submitted by members of the party faction. The main political slogan in the party's election program is "From National Revival to National Upliftment!" The party's "Women's Wing" activists put forward the idea of "Changing Society by Changing People!" as the main idea. In particular, tasks such as creating a continuous education system, turning parliament into a "people's house", raising the status of the state language, and creating favorable working conditions for teachers have been set.

The election program of the "Adolat" Democratic Party of Uzbekistan for 2020-2024 in the field of education includes the following: Knowledge is happiness, ignorance is misfortune! Under the slogan "Women's Wing", activists of the "Women's Wing" have focused strong social policy on human capital, which ensures the great future of our country. Investing in education is an investment in the future, a factor ensuring the well-being of the people, and the competitiveness of the state. Therefore, we are committed to the systematic improvement of the system of continuous education, the provision of high-quality education and upbringing, and the training of highly qualified female personnel.

The Department for Increasing the Political and Legal Activity of Women aims to increase the level of coverage of women in higher education by 50 percent by 2030 by increasing the number of female scholars in state and non-state higher educational institutions, to further increase the number of higher educational institutions, to develop regulatory documents aimed at ensuring the gradual transition of higher educational institutions to self-financing, as well as to include at least 10 higher educational institutions in the list of the first 1,000 higher educational institutions of internationally recognized organizations, including the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University in the list of the first 500 higher educational institutions He put forward the idea of establishing effective and efficient parliamentary, deputy and public control over the measures to introduce women's education. In collaboration with the Ministry of Higher Education, he put forward proposals such as implementing measures to widely introduce correspondence, evening and distance education in all higher educational institutions from 2020 in order to widely cover women [4].

In conclusion, we can say that our country has implemented wide-ranging reforms to ensure and support women's right to education. As a result of the opportunities created in higher education and scientific activities, the socio-political and economic activity of women in society has increased significantly. Raising the legal awareness of women and increasing their activity is an urgent task today, and this process is an important factor in the development of the country. Therefore, every woman should effectively use the opportunities for education and professional growth, be active in protecting her rights and interests. Because educated and qualified women are a solid foundation for the development and future of society..

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